

Solar neutrino fluxes show the signature of planet formation processes

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Kunitomo & Guillot (2021) 655, A51, A&A
Kunitomo, Guillot & Buldgen (2022) 667, L2, A&A

Coevolution of protostar and disk/planet

entropy
materials

thermal
chemical

structures of stars

e.g., Hartmann+1997, Hosokawa+2011,
Baraffe+2009, 2010, 2012, Tognelli+2016

Hartmann+2016

Kunitomo+2017

- Luminosity spreads in clusters
e.g., Hillenbrand2009, Jeffries2012, Cao+2021

Kunitomo+2018

- λ Boo stars e.g., Murphy+Pauzen2017
- Solar twins e.g., Meléndez+2009
- Binaries e.g., Spina+2021

Kunitomo+2021, 2022

- Solar modeling problem

Planet formation processes

I. **~150 M_{\oplus} solids** (97–168 M_{\oplus}) were used for planet formation processes in the Solar System (Kunitomo+2018)

cf. **~5000 M_{\oplus} metals** in the Sun

Planet formation processes

1. **~150 M_⊕ solids** (97–168 M_⊕) were used for planet formation processes in the Solar System (Kunitomo+2018)
2. **Variable composition of accreting materials** due to dust drift

Garaud+2007, Guillot+2014, Applegren+2020, Elbakyan+2020

rapidly fall onto the proto-Sun

Kunitomo+Guillot 2021

How does accretion affects the chemical structure of the Sun?

Method: Stellar evolution simulation & Optimization

- Stellar evolution calculations with MESA code from the protostellar phase to 4.567 Gyr
Paxton+2011, Kunitomo+2017, 2018, 2021
- Optimization with the simplex method *Nelder-Mead1965*
- Two abundances: **low-Z Asplund+2009** (+high-Z Grevesse+Sauval 1998)
see also Asplund+2005, 2021, see however Magg+2022

How models are optimized

Results at 4.567 Gyr

Input parameters

planet formation processes

Results: 3 models

Result 1) Standard solar models

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- Observed constraints favor **high-Z** models
Agostini+2020, Salmon+2021, Orebi-Gann+2021

“Solar modeling problem”
(abundance)

Spectroscopic observations suggest **low-Z** surface
Asplund+2005, 2009, 2021, see however Magg+2022

Result 1) Standard solar models

- Observed constraints favor **high-Z** models

Agostini+2020, Salmon+2021, Orebi-Gann+2021

Result 1) Standard solar models

χ^2

- Observed constraints favor **high-Z** models
Agostini+2020, Salmon+2021, Orebi-Gann+2021
- Our SSMs are different from previous studies because we used **6 observational constraints** (3 in previous studies)
 → Optimization procedure matters!
Kunitomo+Guillot 2021, see also Ayukov+Baturin2017

Result 2) Solar models with opacity increase

- With **~12–18% opacity increase**, $\chi^2 \approx \mathbf{0.5!}$
Kunitomo+Guillot 2021; see also Bahcall+2005, Christensen-Dalsgaard+2009, Bailey+2015, Buldgen+2019
- However, inconsistent with neutrino observation

Kunitomo+2022

Result 3) Models w/ planet formation

- With **~12–18% opacity increase**, $\chi^2 \approx \mathbf{0.5!}$
Kunitomo+Guillot 2021; see also Bahcall+2005, Christensen-Dalsgaard+2009, Bailey+2015, Buldgen+2019
- However, inconsistent with neutrino observation
- Models with **planet formation processes & opacity increase reproduce all the observations**
 (neutrino, helioseismic, and surface abundances)
see also Serenelli+2011, Zhang+2019

Kunitomo+2022

All the fluxes consistent with obs. ($\approx 1\sigma$)

Why does planet formation affect neutrino fluxes?

Higher **metallicity**
 → Higher opacity
 → Higher **temperature**
 → Higher neutrino fluxes

$$\Phi(^8\text{B}) \propto X_{\text{center}} Z_{\text{center}} T_{\text{center}}^{25}$$

$$\Phi(^7\text{Be}) \propto X_{\text{center}} Z_{\text{center}} T_{\text{center}}^{11}$$

$$\Phi(^{13}\text{N}), \Phi(^{15}\text{O}) \propto X_{\text{center}} Z_{\text{center}} T_{\text{center}}^{20}$$

$$\Phi(pp) \propto X_{\text{center}}^2 T_{\text{center}}^4$$

Bahcall+Ulmer96

What governs the central metallicity?

high- Z accretion **low- Z accretion**

What governs the central metallicity?

Central metallicity evolution

high-Z accretion **low-Z accretion**

pebble drift

Masanobu Kunitomo

Solar models w/ planet formation processes

What governs the central metallicity?

high-Z accretion **low-Z accretion**

Radiative core develops
 → central Z is preserved

pebble drift

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high-Z accretion ↔ low-Z accretion

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“Incomplete CNO cycle” ($^{12}\text{C} + 2p \rightarrow ^{14}\text{N}$)
 → central Z increases & convective core

Solar models w/ planet formation processes

What governs the central metallicity?

↔ ↔
high- Z accretion **low- Z accretion**

pebble drift

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**Radiative core develops
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**“Incomplete CNO cycle” ($^{12}\text{C} + 2p \rightarrow ^{14}\text{N}$)
 → central Z increases & convective core**

Gravitational settling → central Z ↑ & surface Z ↓

Solar models w/ planet formation processes

Summary

- We simulated the formation and evolution of the Sun focusing on the effect of planet formation processes on the solar structure
- We found
 - Opacity increase is needed to reproduce helioseismic constraints but decreases neutrino fluxes
 - On the other hand, planet formation processes can increase the central metallicity by up to 5% and affect neutrino fluxes
 - Models including both **planet formation processes** and opacity increase **reproduce all the observational constraints** (spectroscopic/helioseismic/neutrino)

Kunitomo, Guillot & Buldgen, 2022

